

Towards Reverse Engineering User Stories from Code: An LLM Based Investigation: Supplemental Material

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Instructions

The **GroundTruth_UserStory_Code** folder contains two main directories: **Code_Snippets** and **Reference_Stories**.

- **Code_Snippets**: This directory includes subfolders organized by NLOC ranges. Each subfolder contains the code snippets used in this study, saved as .cpp files.
- **Reference_Stories**: This directory contains CSV files for each NLOC range. Each CSV file includes manually generated user stories corresponding to the code snippets.

The **Prompts** file includes the following types of prompts:

- Zero-shot
- Zero-shot-CoT
- One-shot
- One-shot -CoT
- Few-shot
- Few-shot-CoT

Acronyms:

- NLOC stands for Non Commenting Lines of Code
- CoT stands for Chain of Thought reasoning

Figure 1: F1 Score Across Different LLAMA 3.1 Model Parameters and NLOC Ranges.

Figures 2: Precision, Recall, F1 Score Using LLAMA 3.1 70B With and Without CoT Across NLOC Ranges

Table1: Benchmark Comparison of LLaMA and GPT Models

Category	Benchmark	LLaMA 3.1 8B	LLaMA 3.1 70B	LLaMA 3.1 405B	GPT-4	GPT-4 Omni	GPT-3.5
Math	GSM8K (5-shot, CoT)	51.9	95.1	96.8	94.2	96.1	96.4
Tool Use	BFCL	76.1	84.8	88.5	80.3	80.5	90.2
Long Context	NIH/Multi-needle	98.8	97.5	98.1	-	100.0	90.8
Multilingual	Multilingual MGSM	68.9	86.9	91.6	85.9	90.5	51.4
Code	MBPP EvalPlus (base)	72.8	88.6	89.6	86.6	87.8	82.0
Code	HumanEval (0-shot)	72.6	80.5	89.0	86.6	90.2	68.0
Pricing (per 1M tokens)		LLaMA 3.1 8B	LLaMA 3.1 70B	LLaMA 3.1 405B	GPT-4	GPT-4 Omni	GPT-3.5
Input		\$0.05	\$0.65	\$9.50	\$30.00	\$2.50	\$3.00
Output		\$0.25	\$2.75	\$9.50	\$60.00	\$10.00	\$4.00

Description:

A comparison between LLAMA models (8B, 70B, and 405B) and GPT models (GPT-4, GPT-4 Omni, and GPT-3.5) across various benchmarks, with bolding the highest-performing model for each benchmark. Additionally, the cost associated with processing 1 million input and output tokens for each model [1]

Table2: Precision, Recall and F1 score for NLOC Ranges 41–50 and 81–90

Method	Precision (41–50 NLOC)	Recall (41–50 NLOC)	F1 score (41–50 NLOC)	Precision (81–90 NLOC)	Recall (81–90 NLOC)	F1 score (81–90 NLOC)
Zero	0.77	0.74	0.76	0.76	0.71	0.74
Zero_CoT	0.78	0.73	0.76	0.78	0.70	0.74
One	0.78	0.74	0.76	0.77	0.71	0.74
One_CoT	0.77	0.74	0.75	0.76	0.70	0.73
Few	0.79	0.75	0.77	0.77	0.71	0.74
Few_CoT	0.79	0.75	0.77	0.77	0.70	0.73

Description:

Metrics for each NLOC 41-50 and 81-90 with different prompt techniques, highlighting the Hight percentage for each metric across different prompting techniques.

References

[1] Llama.com. (n.d.). *Llama: Open and Efficient Foundation Language Models*. Retrieved December 6, 2024, from <https://www.llama.com>